

EG1 “COMPUTE & STORE”

KEY RESULTS

GERHARD FETTWEIS

FEBRUARY 1, 2022

3RD CORENECT PUBLIC WORKSHOP

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 956830

Mission EG1

What is needed for

- Green
- Trustworthy processing in 5G and beyond?
- At each level of the HW/SW stack?

Identify checks and balances

Consider market situation

System design

Connectivity Infrastructure – Characteristics

- Not “mission-critical”
- High level of reliability, availability and QoS
- High performance
→ More use of discrete components

Connectivity Infrastructure – Trends

- Standardization (JEDEC, PCI-SIG, 6G,...)
 - Push for security + privacy to foster European players
- Research on composition of discrete components
 - Memory hierarchy
 - “Memory-application codesign”
 - MPSoC interconnection
 - Hypervisor
 - Isolation of sensitive data
 - 3D integration

➔ Trustworthy platform-chips

Consumer Grade – Characteristics

- Europe's weakest market segment
- Low cost, backwards-compatible devices
→ Hard to establish new ecosystems
- Increasing number of customers value security and privacy
- Short life-cycle (2-3 y)

Consumer Grade – Trends

- Trustworthy consumer platform-chips
 - European isolation layer beneath established ecosystems
 - “IBM-PC” of mobile platforms
- Storage-over-radio network
- New design paradigms
 - Optimized MPSoC co-design through higher-level stack definition
 - Hybrid memories and 3D integration

Industry Grade – Characteristics

Requirements:

Trustworthy platform-chips/chipsets

- Mission critical
- Safety
- Low latency
- Scalability
- Low energy consumption

Also non-industrial applications with similar requirements

- E.g., “smart home”

Industry Grade – Trends

- eNVM
as low-energy, high-speed memories
- MPSoC
meta-level description standard
- Open low-resource embedded OS
framework
- “Digital design kitchens”
→ Parallel innovation of end-product
and chip platform

Automotive Connectivity – Characteristics

- From mechanics to electronics
- Autonomous driving
- Wireless connectivity

Requirements:

Trustworthy platform-chips/chipsets

- High safety
- High AI performance
- Low latency
- Includes other mission-critical consumer devices
 - E.g., exoskeletons

Automotive Connectivity – Trends

Trustworthy platform-chips/chipsets

- Safety-enhanced ISA
- MPSoC description standard
- Microkernel OS

- AI
 - Embedded memories
 - Privacy respecting data collection

SWOT (Selected)

Strengths

- Telecommunication infrastructure vendors
- Automotive and vertical industries
- eNVM
- MPSoCs and microkernel OS
- Research

Weaknesses

- Consumer devices
- Leading-edge processes
- Slow adaption of new technology trends
- No design house for AI and AI engines
- Nearly no design capability

- Base new systems on European values and ethical principles to improve security and user-controlled privacy
- Privacy regulations integrated into components and data collection infrastructure
- 2.5D and 3D integration
- Novel memory options

- Dependency on outside supply
- Acquisition of innovative SMEs by non-European technology giants
- No market for platform semiconductors
- Decentralized EU unable to keep pace with US and China on AI and more
- EU's industry players not prepared for their own "Tesla-shock"

Opportunities

Threats

EG1 selected key strategic actions

Short term (<2026) → IP development, patents, regulations, and basic research

- Ensure activity in standardization bodies
- Foster digitization of European industries
- Secure access to < 7 nm CMOS technology, design tools, license costs, IP costs
- Improve existing European eNVM and start industrial transfer of new memory technologies
- Develop an MPSoC meta-level description standard for trustworthy integration of third-party IP
- Support development of open modular microkernel-based OS for use in safety and security contexts
- Wake-up European industry segments for their "Tesla-shocks"

Medium term (2026-2030) → Design of solutions

- Collect and organize access to Europe-specific datasets for AI training with components that have privacy regulations integrated
- Establish "digital design kitchens": parallel innovation of end product and chip platform
- Push for isolation mechanisms for sensitive pieces of data in the 6G standard
- Invest in 2.5D and 3D packaging
- Confirm the industrial transfer of new memory technologies
- Push for open accessible hardware platforms to enable replacing individual components with European-grown alternatives
- Develop and deploy a modular microkernel-based secure OS framework

Long term (>2030) → Productization and Selling

- Establish leading-edge technology source in Europe
- Address research questions related to eNVM improvements
- Productize memory technology IP, MPSoCs
- Design a new OS-based software stack definition through higher-level abstraction methods